

Online e-participation in the Global Innovation Index

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Online e-participation, in the context of the Global Innovation Index (GII), refers to the ability of governments to engage citizens in decision-making and public administration through the use of digital technologies, particularly the Internet. This concept encompasses three main dimensions: the availability and accessibility of public information online, the capacity for interaction between citizens and institutions through digital platforms, and the ability for citizens to actively participate in decision-making processes via digital tools. In other words, online e-participation focuses on how governments leverage the potential of the web to promote greater transparency, improve access to public information, and create spaces for dialogue and collaboration with the population. These tools can include portals for public consultation, platforms for submitting suggestions or feedback on laws or policies, and participation in digital deliberative processes, such as online surveys and discussion forums. Within the GII framework, e-participation is considered an important indicator of public sector innovation, as it represents an effective use of technology to improve governance and involve citizens in the democratic process. Countries with high levels of e-participation tend to foster a stronger culture of civic engagement, facilitating access to information and empowering citizens to shape public policies. The level of e-participation varies significantly across countries, reflecting differences in digital infrastructure, the technological skills of the population, and the political willingness to promote the use of technologies for public participation. In summary, online e-participation is a key indicator of a country's ability to integrate digital technologies to strengthen democracy and government innovation. The data refers to the period between 2013 and 2022.

Online e-participation in 2022. The data on online e-participation in 2022 shows a global distribution of countries' digital participation capabilities, with a clear divide between those with advanced digital infrastructures and those with less developed systems. At the top of the rankings are countries like Estonia, South Korea, and the United States, all with a perfect score of 100. These countries are known for their heavy investments in digitization and online public services, creating platforms that allow citizens to interact with institutions efficiently and transparently. Estonia, in particular, is a pioneer in this field with its cutting-edge e-government system, facilitating online participation in almost every aspect of public life. Closely following are Japan and New Zealand, both scoring 98.8, demonstrating that these nations have also implemented robust digital infrastructures that enable citizens to participate in political and civil life through online tools. Other European countries such as Austria, the United Kingdom, and the Netherlands stand out with high scores, confirming Europe's commitment to promoting digital participation. Singapore also ranks highly, thanks to its advanced technological infrastructure and digital development strategy aimed at involving citizens in the decision-making process. An interesting aspect of the data is the presence of some developing or emerging countries, such as China (96.4), Brazil (90.5), and India (85.7), which have achieved relatively high scores. These results indicate that, despite economic and infrastructural challenges, these countries are making significant progress in enabling online participation. China, in particular, has implemented a vast and centralized digital infrastructure, while Brazil and India are leveraging the growth of mobile technologies to expand access to public services and online participation platforms. On the other hand, countries at the lower end of the rankings, such as Mauritania (9.5),

Algeria (15.5), and various sub-Saharan African nations, show a significant lack of development in digital infrastructure and access to technology. These countries face numerous obstacles, including low internet penetration, inadequate infrastructure, and limited access to technological devices. This makes it difficult for citizens in these nations to access e-participation platforms, thus limiting their ability to interact with the government and actively participate in public life. Another relevant finding is the low performance of countries like Iran (46.4) and Nigeria (48.8), which, despite being regional powers, show lower levels of digital participation compared to countries with comparable economies. This can be attributed to various factors, including political restrictions, internet censorship, and digital infrastructures that are not sufficiently developed to support broad civic participation. In summary, the 2022 e-participation data reveals a world where access to and digital participation vary greatly from country to country. Nations with advanced economies and solid technological infrastructures are clearly at an advantage, while many emerging economies are making progress. However, significant disparities remain, particularly in developing countries, where access to technology remains a crucial challenge for civic digital participation.

Online E-participation between 2013 and 2022. The data on online e-participation between 2013 and 2022 shows significant changes in digital engagement across various countries. This period saw extraordinary growth in online participation in many developing nations, reflecting global trends toward greater digital inclusivity, technological advancement, and increased access to the internet. At the same time, some countries, including those with advanced economies, experienced stagnation or even relative declines, highlighting that factors beyond infrastructure alone influence sustained digital participation. One of the most surprising changes is seen in countries like Bulgaria, Rwanda, Namibia, and Angola, which started from very low levels of e-participation (2.6%) in 2013, with exponential increases by 2022. For example, Bulgaria recorded an impressive growth of 3334.62%, reaching an online participation level of 89.3% in 2022. This suggests that Bulgaria made significant investments in digital infrastructure, favorable policies, and public awareness to facilitate citizen engagement through online platforms. Similarly, Rwanda saw a growth of 2326.92%, reaching 63.1% in online participation, highlighting the success of digital initiatives aimed at improving governance and civic participation, despite a weaker economic base compared to more developed nations. The growth in African countries such as Namibia, Angola, Zimbabwe, and Cameroon reflects a positive trend in e-participation in regions that were previously lagging in digital inclusion. These countries saw substantial percentage increases in online engagement, ranging from 1500% to 1800%. The increase in internet penetration, mobile technology adoption, and digital literacy programs are likely key factors driving these changes. However, despite the impressive growth, the overall level of e-participation in these countries remains significantly lower than in more developed nations, indicating that there is still a long way to go to achieve parity with global leaders in digital engagement. Turkey and Cyprus also represent interesting cases of significant growth in e-participation. Both countries recorded notable increases, with Turkey rising from 5.3% in 2013 to 89.3% in 2022 and Cyprus growing from 7.9% to 95.2%. These increases demonstrate how emerging economies, when coupled with strong digital infrastructure and targeted government policies, can make substantial leaps in terms of online participation. This trend highlights the transformative potential of technology, particularly in terms of strengthening civic engagement and improving government transparency. In contrast, many developed nations saw much smaller increases, reflecting either a saturation of participation levels or challenges in maintaining high rates of engagement. For example, the United States and the United Kingdom already had very high levels of e-participation in 2013 (92.1%) and registered only small increases

by 2022. The United States reached 100% online participation, while the UK rose to 97.6%. These figures suggest that these countries have already maximized their digital reach, or that further engagement requires improvements in the quality and inclusivity of participation. It is interesting to note that some countries, such as Germany and Israel, experienced a decline in online participation during this period. Germany's score dropped slightly from 76.3% to 75%, while Israel saw a more significant decrease from 89.5% to 71.4%. These declines suggest that even in technologically advanced countries, maintaining high levels of online engagement can be challenging and is likely influenced by multiple factors, including political, cultural, or social dynamics that affect how citizens interact with digital platforms. At the bottom of the ranking, countries like Mongolia and Ethiopia saw negligible changes or small declines in their participation rates. This stagnation could be due to limited infrastructure development, restrictive government policies, or socio-economic challenges that prevent broader digital participation among citizens. In summary, the data reveals a mixed global landscape in terms of online e-participation, with developing nations experiencing some of the highest growth rates, reflecting increasing access to digital platforms. In contrast, many advanced economies appear to have reached a saturation point or show declines, suggesting that maintaining continuous engagement requires more than just digital infrastructure. This indicates that while technology can bridge the participation gap, sustained engagement depends on a combination of political, social, and economic factors.

Conclusions. Online e-participation has grown on average in the countries considered, from 33.3% in 2013 to 72.11% in 2023, representing a growth of 116.06%. The top performers are Bulgaria with +3334.62%, Rwanda with +2326.92%, Namibia with +1823.08%, Angola with +1638.46%, and Zimbabwe with +1638.46%. The countries that recorded the worst performances are: Ethiopia with -2.63%, the Netherlands with -3.60%, Kazakhstan with -6.97%, Israel with -20.22%, and Egypt with -25.15%.

Database: Global Innovation Index, accessed on 13 October 2024.

<https://prosperitydata360.worldbank.org/en/indicator/WIPO+GII+61>

Performance	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performers	Bulgaria	★ 2,6	☆ 89,3	☆ 86,7	★ 3334,62
	Rwanda	★ 2,6	☆ 63,1	☆ 60,5	★ 2326,92
	Namibia	★ 2,6	☆ 50	☆ 47,4	★ 1823,08
	Angola	★ 2,6	☆ 45,2	☆ 42,6	★ 1638,46
	Zimbabwe	★ 2,6	☆ 45,2	☆ 42,6	★ 1638,46
Worse Performers	Ethiopia	☆ 34,2	☆ 33,3	★ -0,9	★ -2,63
	Netherlands	☆ 100	☆ 96,4	★ -3,6	★ -3,60
	Kazakhstan	☆ 94,7	☆ 88,1	★ -6,6	★ -6,97
	Israel	☆ 89,5	☆ 71,4	★ -18,1	★ -20,22
	Egypt, Arab Rep.	☆ 68,4	☆ 51,2	★ -17,2	★ -25,15

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